

Research Article

Assessing the Impact of Chinese Investment in Africa; A Case Study of Developmental Projects in Ghana

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Abstract: The main purpose of this study is to ascertain the impact of Chinese financing projects on various indicators in Africa and the economic development of the countries. To achieve the required objectives of the study, the study included the descriptive statistical research design which comprises of the qualitative and quantitative procedures for data gathering and analysis. The sample size of the study is 180 and the primary data were collected by using the stratified and purposive sampling technique. The study has revealed some major findings namely: (a) according to the mean rank of the characteristics of the Chinese foreign direct investment (FDI) in Ghana were found to be influenced to the indirect FDI investment with Chinese SOE, bilateral investment in public projects, and outsource contracts to Chinese Companies; (b) the influence of Chinese finance development on the Ghanaian businesses as rated very important by the respondents are supporting Infrastructure development, improve SMEs relationship development, and competitive impact; (c) the major challenges affecting adversely of Chinese investment in Ghana were found to be as political situation, local prices and inflation, and environmental Issues; (d) the necessary strategies which could improve Chinese investment were identified as seek Chinese FDI to help fund industrial and commercial construction in the private sector, framework for investment to impact on the economy much more, and improving on transparency framework for China FDI. The research study also showed that there has been progress in infrastructural development in Ghana as a result of the Chinese investment. Major policy implications are further deliberated.

Keywords: Ghana, economic development, financing projects, foreign direct investment (FDI), China.

1. Introduction

There has been economic and trade relationship between China and African countries dating back to early 1900s. This was the period when Chinese navigator Zheng He reach the coast of Africa and opened a whole new opportunity in few African countries; Kenya, Somalia. There has been further enhancement of relationship with the 1949 conference of Bandung, which increased the China's economic interest in other developing countries on the African continent. Over the years between 1970s and 1990s, there has been minute incremental support and

partnership between some African countries and China, with mostly the Chinese government sending economic support to countries Africa. However, in 2009, there was a detailed investigation and research conducted by World Bank on developing countries concerning infrastructure development, standard of living and economic development. The study revealed various challenges facing African countries as well great resource opportunities. The latter really gave China the necessary fully-grown interest in the benefits and gains in helping to develop infrastructure and business relationship with some selected African countries. Some analyses were made to ascertain what African countries needs and it was pegged at \$93billion. According to Meyer (2012), foreign direct investment (FDI) is defined as investment into business units in another country with an equity stake sufficient to influence the strategy of the foreign business.

Nonetheless, China's engagement in Africa has been growing in many aspects such as trade, investment, and aid. Over the last decade, although the traditional partners of the African countries, namely the European Union and the United States, continue to dominate foreign direct investment (FDI) in Africa, the rise of China is highly noticeable. For instance, from 2003 to 2011, the flow of Chinese investment to Africa grew by more than 30 times, while that of the United States grew by about one third (UNCTAD Bilateral FDI Statistics, 2014). In Africa, according to Sautman and Hairong (2017), China has the highest return on FDI, ranging from 29% in 1990 to 40% in 2015. Although China's trade with Africa is small compared to US\$1.76 trillion in world trade, it has grown from US\$3 billion in 1995 to US\$55 billion in 2006. It is predicted that Chinese investment will top the US\$100 billion mark by the end of the decade. As evidence of this trend, there are more than 800 Chinese companies in Africa in 2016, one hundred of which are medium to large state owned firms while some companies have started illegal mining in Ghana. (Taylor, 2016).

More recently, Chinese companies are mining oil in Angola and Sudan, building roads in Ethiopia, generating electricity in Kenya, building infrastructure and encouraging tourism in Sierra Leone, and servicing mobile phones in Kenya and Nigeria. China's rapidly developing oil consumption seems to have a bigger effect on Chinese-African trade (McLeary, 2017). This is the main reason behind the whole raft of new contracts between 2002 and 2016. During this period, Chinese oil companies have signed deals to buy refineries and explore oil and gas in Algeria, Gabon, Angola, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Congo Brazzaville, Namibia, Ethiopia, Madagascar and Sudan. Recently, China and Nigeria just signed a major oil deal worth US\$23 billion (Swartz and Hall 2014). It calls for China to build three refineries in Nigeria. As a result, trade between them has increased making China the continent's third largest trading partner after the European Union and the US. China has continued to push closer ties with Africa and has awarded US\$10 billion in aid for the next three years and dispatched volunteers to provide medical assistance and build hospitals and schools (Ewing, 2009). As Tull (2016) explains, Western criticisms of China's human rights record and other international issues have induced the Chinese to seek closer ties with non-western nations in an effort to build international coalitions. The trend and focus of Chinese engagements with Africa have changed during the last five years. As Chinese economic growth slows down and more emphasis is given to the development of hi-tech industries, raw material imports from Africa to China decrease rapidly. While China imported minerals and petroleum worth US\$62.07 billion in 2011, counting for 66.58% of its total imports from Africa, the value of imported minerals and petroleum dropped to US\$35.37 billion in 2015. However, Chinese investment in Africa kept growing steadily during the same period. China's outward foreign direct investment (FDI) stock in Africa grew from US\$16.24 billion in 2011 to US\$34.69 billion in 2015.

Therefore, the main objective of this study is to ascertain the impact of Chinese financing projects on various indicators in Africa and the economic development of the countries. In details, the specific objectives of the study includes to ascertain the characteristics of Chinese investment on the economic development of Ghana, determine the overall impact of Chinese finance investment on the Ghanaian businesses and economic development, and to establish strategies to enhance Chinese investment for mutual economic partnership in Ghana.

2. Literature Review

Examination has been carried out to ascertain the impact of Chinese financing projects on various indicators in Africa and the economic development of the countries. Many studies have argued that Sino-African cooperation is mutually advantageous (Aguilar and Goldstein, 2009; Carolina and Murphey, 2009; Jing, 2009; Wu and Cheng, 2010; Zhao, 2008). Yin and Vaschetto (2011) explained that the interests of China and Africa have been reconciled through beneficial, exploratory and win-win business partnerships. The growth of Chinese investment in African countries has been growing steadily over a period of time. Klaver and Trebilcock (2011) analyze the Chinese investment in Africa, and they point out seven ways Chinese investment contribute to African growth: commodity prices (China's demand for resources raised commodity prices), capacity to extract (many African countries lack the capacity to extract their own resources), infrastructure (China's contribution to African development is arguably most significant in infrastructure), manufacturing (Chinese investment has potential to develop Africa's manufacturing sector), employment (Chinese investment creates employment), market access (China improves Africa's access to its market by reducing Chinese tariffs), and consumers (Chinese FDI benefits African consumers by lowering prices of manufactured goods and food).

The trajectory path of growth for many African countries, including Ghana, has been the growth and increment in Foreign direct investment (FDI) from other well – established countries with sufficient resources (Robinson, 2012). According to Mello and Fedi (2015), FDI has been an important source of economic growth for Ghana, bringing in capital investment, technology and management knowledge needed for economic growth. Bayraktar (2014) indicated that International capital financial investment or inflows associated with investments in firms in which a foreign investor acquires a controlling stake classified as direct investments and those associated with purchases of stocks or bonds without a controlling stake as portfolio or equity investments. In most cases, financial investment is given to countries through infrastructure development and sometimes supporting the economy or budget (Redine, 2016). According to UNCTAD (2019), FDI flows to Africa rose by 11 per cent to \$46 billion, despite declines in many of the larger recipient countries. The increase was supported by continued resource-seeking inflows, some diversified investments and a recovery in South Africa after several years of low-level inflows. According to Asymta (2014), A foreign direct investment (FDI) is an investment made by a firm or individual in one country into business interests located in another country. Generally, FDI takes place when an investor establishes foreign business operations or acquires foreign business assets in a foreign company. However, FDIs are distinguished from portfolio investments in which an investor merely purchases equities of foreign-based companies. In addition, Klaver and Trebicock (2012) dealt with the resources for infrastructure deals; that is, the benefits of China's contribution to African infrastructure may be exceeded by the high costs. Secondly, Chinese FDI may provide few spillovers in technology, skills, and employment. Lastly, Chinese FDI may deindustrialize Africa by out-competing African firms given that African manufacturing is already weak.

Analyzing China-Africa relations, Ademola et al. (2009) conclude that the negative effects may outweigh the positive ones for many African countries, but without econometric analyses.

Moreover, Chinese investments and contracts in sub-Saharan Africa totaled \$299 billion from 2005 to 2018, according to the China Investment Global Tracker, and in 2018, Chinese president Xi Jinping vowed to invest an additional \$60 billion in African nations (UNCTAD, 2019). If the continent can successfully navigate the issues raised by Chinese neo-colonial ambitions—such as the fear of “debt trap” diplomacy, with \$130 billion in loans from China to African nations since 2000—they will be able to ascend from this trajectory into global power. The pledge for China to continue investing in Africa has received much boost year over year, with a recent announcement China has continued to push closer ties with Africa and has awarded US\$100 billion in aid for the next three years and dispatched volunteers to provide medical assistance and build hospitals and schools (Ewing, 2019) Building infrastructure and encouraging tourism in Sierra Leone, and servicing mobile phones in Kenya and Nigeria. China’s rapidly developing oil consumption seems to have a bigger effect on Chinese-African trade (Taylor, 2006; McLeary, 2007). This is the main reason behind the whole raft of new contracts between 2002 and 2006. During this period, Chinese oil companies have signed deals to buy refineries and explore oil and gas in Algeria, Gabon, Angola, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Congo Brazzaville, Namibia, Ethiopia, Madagascar and Sudan. Additionally, China also helped in treating infectious diseases such as malaria and HIV/AIDS and launched the first overseas radio station in Kenya (Brooks and Shin, 2006). Recently, China and Nigeria just signed a major oil deal worth US\$23 billion (Swartz and Hall 2010). It calls for China to build three refineries in Nigeria.

According to Tukić (2013) attribute China’s increasing involvement in Africa’s infrastructure space to two factors. Firstly, its saturated domestic construction industry has prompted Chinese firms to look for opportunities elsewhere. Secondly, the development of Africa’s infrastructure allows China’s private firms and SOEs to gain access to the continent’s relatively untapped and unsaturated infrastructure and consumer markets. Thus, African scholars and leadership have raised questions and instigated speculations concerning the interest China has showed in the investment in Africa (Asamoah, 2014). Likewise, China’s increased presence in Africa has been questioned by several African scholars and societal organizations (Konings, 2007). While some scholars see China’s economic growth as a positive development model for the third world (Alden, 2005), others look more critically at China’s behavior on the continent and sees its parallels to the neo-colonial past (De Lorenzo, 2007). We will use the Hood and Young (1981) model that evaluate multinational activity based on social, competitive, trade, etc. criteria.

Therefore, assessing the advantages and disadvantages of Chinese involvement in Africa may not be so simple. Africa’s economic growth of 25.8 percent in 2017, the highest ever may partially be attributed to Chinese investment (Hanson, 2018). It has cancelled debt worth US\$10 billion from African countries, sent doctors to treat Africans, and hosted thousands of African workers and students in their universities and training centers. There are even more controversial points however. These are related to the trade, commerce, and social areas. According to Kaplisky and et al. (2017), in trade, especially Sub-Saharan Africa is impacted in two ways. The use of Chinese labor, rather than local workers in Chinese sponsored projects in Ethiopia, Sudan and Namibia has been criticized locally (Alden, 2015). De Lorenzo (2017) also reiterates that, what is worrisome is the impact of Chinese competition on African enterprises and exports. The challenges are not limited to the competition. According to Anshan

(2017), with the flow of goods from China, conflict over labor practice and market strategies is turning out to be an important issue.

3. Methodology of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to ascertain the impact of Chinese financing projects on various indicators in Africa and the economic development of the countries. To achieve the required objectives of the study, the study included the descriptive statistical research design which comprises of the qualitative and quantitative procedures for data gathering and analysis. Also, the study was a descriptive research design because it evaluates the answers for the question of what impact has the china's investment been to Africa and specifically Ghana. The sample size of the study is 180 and the data were collected by using the stratified and purposive sampling technique. Furthermore, the research instruments used for data gathering were questionnaires. These questionnaires were grouped into different sets which were opened and closed ended questions. According to Gujarati (2014), questionnaires are set of questions which are formulated to solicit information from the selected respondents of a specific research study. The questionnaires were constructed in context of the objectives of the research study guides the research work. With the data gathered and various impact responses given by the selected respondents, analysis done using the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) version 23. The analysis was made through the descriptive frequency analysis of statistical tables and charts whiles generating a regression analysis between the variables for the objectives.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Demographic Information

Variable	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	126	70.0
	Female	54	30.0
Educational qualification	MPhil	8	4.4
	Masters certificate	53	29.4
	First degree	78	43.3
	Diploma	38	21.1
	Others	3	1.7
Position held in the institution	Administrator	14	7.8
	Management	54	30.0
	Employee	68	37.8
	Director	37	20.6
	Others	7	3.9

Source: Field survey, 2020

Table 1 shows the demographic information of the respondents. The empirical findings display that 70.00% of the respondents are male, while 30.00% of them are female. In terms of educational qualification, 43.30% of the respondents had first degree, 29.40% of them had masters certificate, and 21.10% of them had a diploma degree, and only around of 5.00% of them had an MPhil degree among the respondents. Moreover, the highest percentage of the respondents are worked in the institution as an employee, management, director of the

organization, and administrator accounted for 37.80%, 30.00%, 20.60%, and 7.80% respectively.

4.2 Progress or Advancement of Chinese FDI

Moreover, the researcher queried the respondents to give a general overview of the trend and progress of the Chinese investment in Ghana. This is their own introspection on what the outlooks of the investments are over the period of time. Figure 1 shows the progress and advancement of Chinese FDI in Ghana, majority of the respondents 34.4% indicated certainly there is progress and or advancement of Chinese FDI in Ghana, while those who indicated very impressive progress were 29.44%, the not impressive response was 23.33%) while, the least of the response was somehow showing 12.878% of the respondents. This data clearly backs the assertion made by Asimo (2016) concerning growth of Chinese FDI and the impact on advancement and economic development of recipient countries, while the responses for the research study showed a diverging view coming from the scholarly works of Moany (2018) on the negative advantage being taken by the Chinese due to the FDI they have made in West African countries. Another assertion to back the findings comes from Yingyi (2019) who reiterated the continued grow of investment from China in order African countries – Tanzania, Kenya, Nigeria and Ghana which have seen growth and progress.

Figure 1. Progress or Advancement of Chinese FDI

4.3 Major Characteristics of Chinese FDI

From the Table 2, it is seen that according to the mean rank of the characteristics of the Chinese foreign direct investment (FDI) in Ghana, indirect FDI finance with Chinese SOE is in the 1st position with a 3.46 mean scores followed by bilateral investment in public projects with 3.24 mean scores, outsource contracts to Chinese Companies with 3.20 average scores, direct cash investment with 2.67 mean scores, local private company investment with 2.39 mean scores, and financing projects without Chinese companies partaking with 2.35 mean scores. The findings of the study is in line with the assertions made by Guluzade (2018), SOEs are frequently utilized as a mechanism for implementing policy, providing socioeconomic stability and building infrastructure in developing countries that Chinese investments are being made. The present study was also backed by the declaration made by Robins (2018) about the Chinese

FDI on the African continent, which is centered mostly on direct investment like roads, ports and harbors activities to boost GDP of recipient countries. Moreover, the outputs of the study indicated or agreed with Martison (2017) and Stevenson (2018) who both evaluated the Chinese FDI and loans to African countries to ascertain that most of the contracts are outsourced to private companies in China as well as state own corporations. Therefore, according to Amigaed (2018) who evaluated the Chinese investment in Africa and how much it accounts for as well the motive which some of them is imputed to have bilateral relationship between China and other countries.

Table 2. Mean Rank of the Characteristics of Chinese FDI

SL	Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	Indirect FDI investment with Chinese SOE	3.46	1.213	1
2	Direct cash investment	2.67	1.219	4
3	Outsource contracts to Chinese Companies	3.20	1.424	3
4	Local private company investment	2.39	1.184	5
5	Bilateral investment in public projects	3.24	1.266	2
6	Financing projects without Chinese companies partaking	2.35	1.136	6

Source: Field survey, 2020

4.4 Impact of Chinese Finance on Economic Development

Table 3. Impact of Chinese Finance on Economic Development

SL	Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	Increase in the GDP growth	2.75	1.246	5
2	Supporting Infrastructure development	3.51	1.271	1
3	Improve SMEs relationship development	3.22	1.407	2
4	Complementary impact, thus supporting local companies	2.85	1.022	4
5	Competitive impact, thus competition with local companies	3.11	1.370	3

Source: Field survey, 2020

Table 3 displays the influence of Chinese finance development on the Ghanaian businesses. The findings of the study showed that the supporting infrastructure development was found the highest correlative ranked with a mean 3.51 and standard deviation of 1.271. This clearly shows that the Chinese investment impacts on supporting infrastructure development. The 2nd ranked mean has to do with Improvement of SMEs relationship development with a mean value of 3.22, on the 3rd ranked mean was 3.11 which correlates to the complementary impact given to local companies, thus supporting local companies over a period of time with a mean 2.85 the 4th. Therefore, it can be said that among the impact on economic development the 5th least of them was the increase in the GDP growth with a mean value of 2.75.

4.5 Major Challenges of Chinese Investment in Ghana

Table 4. Major Challenges of Chinese Investment in Ghana

SL	Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	Environmental Issues, negative impact of Chinese businesses and companies.	3.04	1.396	3
2	Local prices and inflation, crowding out local companies and businesses.	3.17	1.394	2
3	Corruption, this comes in the form of disbursement of funds and implementation of business.	3.03	1.191	4
4	Labor Issues, this happens when local labor are neglected for Chinese ones.	2.72	1.277	5
5	Political Situation, change in political party affecting implementation of Chinese FDI in Ghana.	3.25	1.311	1

Source: Field survey, 2020

After examining the influence of Chinese finance development on the Ghanaian businesses, at this stage, it is essential to know the major challenges of Chinese investment in Ghana, as can be shown in Table 4. The empirical findings indicated that the political situation, change in political party affecting implementation of Chinese FDI in Ghana, local prices and inflation, crowding out local companies and businesses, environmental Issues, negative impact of Chinese businesses and companies, corruption, this comes in the form of disbursement of funds and implementation of business, and labor issues are considered critical challenges for the Chinese investment in Ghana.

4.6 Strategies to Enhance Chinese Investment

Table 5. Strategies to Enhance Chinese Investment

SL	Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	Identifying Partnership Policies on Chinese FDI to include local companies	3.43	1.394	4
2	Framework for investment to impact on the economy much more.	3.67	1.250	2
3	Funding local companies to participate in China FDI projects	2.51	1.184	5
4	Improving on transparency framework for China FDI	3.64	1.364	3
5	Seek Chinese FDI to help fund industrial and commercial construction in the private sector	3.88	1.130	1

Source: Field survey, 2020

To ascertain the necessary strategies which could improve Chinese investment for mutual economic partnership in Ghana is very important at this stage. From the data gathered and showed up in table 4.7 below, the highest ranked factor which gained much acclamation of importance from the respondents was Chinese FDI for industrial and commercial sectors with a mean 3.88. Which represents the closeness to the mean and very high validity of the response. This comes in the form of industrial investment, manufacturing capacity boost as well as expansion of exports in many areas or sectors of the economy. The 2nd ranked mean value of 3.67, also showed that there is need for framework for investment. However, the need to

ascertain the framework for investment from China is very crucial to ascertain the value for money and the impact on the Ghanaian GDP. Some of the framework will expunge the data on the need for proper analysis on usage and value of the financial details. The 3rd rank of mean factors has to do with transparency framework on the investment from China. The mean for this factor is 3.64 which indicated a strong data of closeness to the mean of the respondents agree to the assertion. The data also showed that to avert corruption practices and misappropriation of funds. The Government of Ghana needs to put in place efficient strategies on transparency on utilization of investment resources. On the 4th ranked mean depicting the importance of overall strategies to enhance Chinese investment, identifying partnership policies proved to be very critical. This came up with a mean 3.43. This means that there is the need to formulate partnership policies between businesses and corporate and China and Ghana through the investment procedures. Therefore, the 5th ranked mean shows that funding local companies was much critical but it received the lowest mean 2.51. Also, in many instances investment framework helps to shape the necessary areas or sectors needing the right investment. Moreover, the ranking of the means on the various cohorts was backed by the scholarly work conducted by (Xiaoyang, 2018) who ascertained that most countries will benefit from Investment from China if they have strongly industrial and manufacturing sectors to harness all the necessary resources into these sectors. This was also in line with what Tagom (2018) asserted that most countries in developing world should enhance and grow their manufacturing and industrials sectors to improve on GDP and be self-sufficient.

5. Conclusions and Managerial Implications of the Study

The research study showed that there has been progress in infrastructural development in Ghana as a result of the Chinese investment. Majority of the investment goes into road, railway, tourism development, security service buildings and other infrastructural investment have been boosted by the investment and funding from China. In furtherance, majority of the Chinese investment does not involve local business, SMEs and other local enterprise participation as the central part of the contractual agreement, however, most of the investment have Chinese SOEs who plays a major role in delegating or outsourcing other contracts to local companies in Ghana. Strategic partnership between China and Ghana has led to increase in investment in recent period of time. Thus, bilateral trades also serve as part of the Chinese investment in Ghana. Chinese investment serves as a boost for GDP growth, however on a comparatively small scale to infrastructural development which has been the main rubrics of Chinese investment framework over the recent period of time.

To successfully complete the research study, the summary of findings and conclusion have been drawn, the research went further to make these recommendations for the research study; the research recommends that there is the need for Ghana to develop a strategic plan to help shift Chinese investment into Industrial, manufacturing and other form of finished products enterprises and businesses. This in the long run will help transform the national capacity to handle other form of business without much support from foreign countries in the long run. With Chinese investment going into Ghana's natural resources, it's good for the rise in commodity prices. However, there is the need for transparency framework to govern this investment to avert any form of corrupt practices which might ensue due to the government official's involvement in the signing and initiation of the contracts. One other recommendation deals with the need for authorities at the Ministry of Finance and National Board for Small Scale Industries to help build the capacities of SMEs and business through Chinese partnership to expand to major international markets with adequate funding and technical support. Lastly, there is the need for Ghana and China to have peer review systems in place to monitor the track

record of investment and delve into areas or sectors which will be of major benefit to their partnership aside bilateral trade. Ensuring major manufacturing plants of Chinese companies to be sited in Ghana to serve the Sub – Saharan Region as a form of investment will boost economic growth and development in the long term.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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